

and social networks that they created. Therefore, this paper explores phenomena of biographical networks among these person objects. In order to perform BNA with the data set, there are stages such as obtaining biographic data, modeling and visualizing it.

The current work, thus, focuses on three questions:

- a) How to reach biographical data in Deutsche National Bibliothek (DNB-GND) via Lobid platform (Pohl and Steeg 2018)?,
- b) How to process the biographical data via related Python Libraries?
- c) How to visualize the biographical networks of the persons via graph database, Neo4j?

As a result of the study, information such as birth, death, places of activity, professional relationships and places of exile in the biographical data of the persons are extracted and network visualizations and clusters are obtained with Neo4j (See Image 1 below). With these network visualizations, it is explored in which locations and contexts the persons were located and in which contexts they formed potential networks.

References

- Armitage, Neil. 2016. "The Biographical Network Method." *Sociological Research Online* 21 (2): 165–79. <https://doi.org/10.5153/sro.3827>.
- Bernád, Ágoston Zénó, and Maximilian Kaiser. 2017. "The Biographical Formula: Types and Dimensions of Biographical Networks." In *BD-2017 Biographical Data in a Digital World 2017. Proceedings of the Second Conference on Biographical Data in a Digital World 2017*, CEUR Workshop Proceedings 2119, 45–52. Linz, Austria: CEUR.
- Brouwer, Judith, and Harm Nijboer. 2017. "Golden Agents. A Web of Linked Biographical Data for the Dutch Golden Age." In *Proceedings of the Second Conference on Biographical Data in a Digital World 2017*, edited by Antske Fokkens, Serge ter Braake, Ronald Sluijter, Paul Arthur, and Eveline Wandl-Vogt, 2119:33–38. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. Linz, Austria: CEUR. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2119/#paper6>.
- Fokkens, Antske, and Serge ter Braake. 2017. "Connecting People Across Borders: A Repository for Biographical Data Models." In *Proceedings of the Second Conference on Biographical Data in a Digital World 2017*, edited by Antske Fokkens, Serge ter Braake, Ronald Sluijter, Paul Arthur, and Eveline Wandl-Vogt, 2119:83–92. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. Linz, Austria: CEUR. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2119/#paper13>.
- Leskinen, Petri, Eero Hyvönen, and Jouni Tuominen. 2017. "Analyzing and Visualizing Prosopographical Linked Data Based on Biographies." In *Proceedings of the Second Conference on Biographical Data in a Digital World 2017*, edited by Antske Fokkens, Serge ter Braake, Ronald Sluijter, Paul Arthur, and Eveline Wandl-Vogt, 2119:39–44. CEUR Workshop Proceedings. Linz, Austria: CEUR. <https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2119/#paper7>.
- Pohl, Adrian, and Fabian Steeg. 2018. "lobid-gnd: Suche und Navigation." *lobid.org (blog)*. July 4, 2018. <https://hbz.github.io/lobid-blog/2018/07/04/lobid-gnd-suche.html>.
- Tamper, Minna, Petri Leskinen, and Eero Hyvönen. 2023. "Visualizing and Analyzing Networks of Named Entities in Biographical Dictionaries for Digital Humanities Research." In *Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Text Processing*, edited by Alexander Gelbukh, 199–214. Lecture Notes in Computer Science. Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-24337-0_15.